

Exploiting GNN and DRL for online service provisioning over Elastic Optical Networks

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Abstract—The dynamic provisioning of network services across Data Centers (DCs) interconnected by an Elastic Optical Network (EON) remains a challenging problem, as it requires the orchestration of computing resources in DCs and spectrum resources on optical links. This work proposes a solution based on Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for autonomous provisioning of network services. The proposed solution includes a GNN to extract the topological features of the DC-EON network topology and a DRL agent for the simultaneous and efficient selection of the DCs to host the VNFs and the lightpaths connecting them. The experimental results show that the proposed solution achieves faster convergence and reward than another DRL-based solution in the training phase. Our proposed solution also outperforms a heuristic algorithm and the other DRL solution for provisioning network services on an EON-connected DC in terms of service blocking rate.

Index Terms—Software Defined Networking, Network Function Virtualization, Elastic Optical Networks, Deep Reinforcement Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid deployment and evolution of emerging communications networks, such as 5G and 6G, the network management systems landscape is changing significantly. The deployment of dedicated virtual networks, known as network slices, enables more agile management and efficient resource allocation to meet specific service requirements, while improving network scalability and service provisioning. In this context, the effective placement of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) in geographically distributed Data Centers (DCs) plays a key role in the deployment of services in new generation networks. Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) have emerged as one of the most suitable solutions for interconnecting DCs, due to their huge bandwidth and fine-grained spectrum allocation. In EONs, lightpaths can be established with a spectrum granularity of 6.25 or 12.5 GHz to accommodate heterogeneous bandwidth demands. Enabling VNF-oriented network services on EONs is a complex issue, since it requires choosing a suitable DC for VNF allocation and establishing lightpaths

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using routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) algorithms to connect the VNFs. Thus, this challenging issue implies finding an optimal mapping of virtual nodes and links to physical network nodes and links while considering some constraints such as resource utilization in the DCs and spectrum continuity and contiguity in the EON.

Incorporating artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques also assists network management systems to deal more efficiently and automatically with the complexity and dynamics of emerging networks. Recently, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques have proven effective in solving a variety of network management problems, such as the VFN placement problem or RSA in EONs, which are known to be NP-hard [1], [2]. In DRL, it is well known that input state representation and feature extraction are essential for the algorithm performance. Simple state representation or manual feature extraction are not suitable for graph-structured data. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are a type of neural network dedicated to graph-structured data. GNNs have demonstrated good performance in a wide range of applications, including node classification, graph classification and link prediction [3].

This paper presents a new approach that utilizes DRL and GNN to autonomously provision network services across distributed DCs that are interconnected by an EON. The proposed approach includes a GNN to extract the topological features and a DRL agent to efficiently select simultaneously the DCs to host the VNFs and the lightpaths connecting them. It also enhances our previous proposed solution [4], by transitioning from two separate DRL agents to a single agent capable of simultaneously executing two actions through a multidiscrete action space. The performance of the proposed solution is compared to our previous DRL solution and a heuristic algorithm in terms of service blocking rate.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The graph $G(N, L)$ models the topology of DCs connected by the EON. In this graph, N is the set of optical switching nodes, specifically Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs), that have a DC attached, and L is the set of optical links that interconnect pairs of optical nodes. Each DC has a compute capacity C_n to provision VNFs. Likewise, each link $l \in L$ has F available frequency slots (FS) and a communication latency given by D . On the other hand, a network service request is represented as a VNF Forwarding

needed, which depends on the physical distance of the path [5]. Each VNF instance can require [1, 5, 10] CPU cores. We assumed a realistic scenario where service requests follow a Poisson process and the lifetime of a deployed network service follows an exponential distribution. We fixed the inter-arrival time and varied the lifetime to generate different loads. For training purposes, we implemented our DRL agent using the PPO algorithm with a multidiscrete action space to get the two actions, the learning rate was 10^{-5} , the discount factor was 0.95 and the batch size was 256. We used a graph convolutional network (GCN) with 14 message passing layers as GNN to ensure the aggregation of information from all nodes in the topology. The fully connected neural network consisted of 5 hidden layers with 128 neurons. A training episode involved provisioning 5,000 service requests.

Fig. 3. Training for DRL and GNN-DRL approaches

Fig. 4. Network Service (NS) Blocking for heuristic, DRL and GNN-DRL

We first evaluate the training performance of our GNN DRL agent and compare it with a previous proposed DRL agent [4]. The DRL agent employs a traditional DNN based on linear structures, and thus cannot operate directly on graph-structured data. This agent relies on hand-crafted feature extraction to build the observation space. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the mean reward per episode of both agents. Our GNN DRL solution overcomes the other DRL agent by attaining

a higher episode reward, and also converges faster than the traditional DRL architecture, because it directly operates on graph-structured data.

Then, the online provisioning of service requests was conducted with the trained model. We compare the performance of our proposed GNN-DRL approach with respect to a heuristic algorithm and the DRL agent under different traffic loads. The heuristic benchmark algorithm selects DC with more available computing resources, as long as they satisfy latency and bandwidth constraints. After that, it computes the lightpaths using the k-shortest path algorithm. Figure 4 presents the service blocking when provisioning 5,000 network services using the three approaches. This process was repeated 10 times to ensure the statistical accuracy of our results. Note that, our GNN DRL agent clearly outperforms (i.e., obtains lower blocking) the other two solutions regardless of the requested load. For instance, at a traffic intensity of under 75 Erlangs, the GNN DRL achieves the lowest blocking rate of 0.09. Compared to the heuristic algorithm and the DRL agent, this represents a 53.44% and 26.8% improvement in the blocking rate, respectively. This improvement is attributed to the GNN’s ability to capture a comprehensive view of the network topology, allowing the agent to make more informed and optimal placement decisions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a novel approach is proposed to provision network services across DCs connected by an EON. The solution leverages a GNN to operate on the graph-structured data and extract the features of the DC-EON network topology within the DRL design. The proposed DRL agent is able to select two actions simultaneously through a multidiscrete action space, selecting both the DCs and the lightpaths. This promotes faster decision-making, improves coordination, and simplifies the overall architecture. The simulation results indicate that the proposed solution achieves faster convergence during the training phase compared to a DRL agent that relies on traditional linear DNNs. In addition, due to the improved GNN feature extraction in the construction of the observation space, our solution achieves a lower service blocking rate than a heuristic and another DRL solution for provisioning of network services on an EON-connected DCs. The proposed approach offers a promising solution for deploying VNF-oriented services in dynamic and resource-constrained DC-EON environments.

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